

CLINICAL EFFICACY & VARIOUS TREATMENTS OF SENSORINEURAL HEARING LOSS AND ITS ASSOCIATION WITH METABOLIC SYNDROME

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6345763>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 10th February 2022

Accepted: 15th February 2022

Online: 19th February 2022

KEY WORDS

*Clinic efficacy,
sensorineural hearing
loss, various treatments,
metabolic syndrome*

ABSTRACT

This research article aims to analyze the clinical efficiency of several medical therapies to treat sensorineural hearing loss. Association of sensorineural hearing loss and metabolic syndrome is shown. Hearing defeat is increasing at an exponential rate. Damage to human sensory hair cells and SGNs is usually permanent. It is treated with a variety of medical therapy. DNA coding for a neurotrophic protein is transferred into cochlear cells when electricity is applied. The circular window of cochlea is being studied for pharmaceutical supply. SGNs are protected against degeneration by their slow-release and high-payload medication delivery capabilities. A novel viral vector and gene-editing technique have restored hearing in mice with genetic hearing loss. SGN repopulation and neurotrophin supply, as well as hearing loss, have all been investigated. These and other developments in pharmaceutical treatment will facilitate the translation of pre-clinical results into clinical trials. Hearing loss is considered a complication of metabolic syndrome. Hearing loss is more likely in those with metabolic syndrome.

Introduction

When sound waves are collected, converted to vibrations, and sent to the brain as impulses, you can hear. Hearing loss is characterized according to which portion of the process is impacted. The external or middle ear issues cause a conductive hearing loss. A surgical repair may sometimes help to enhance hearing. Hearing loss induced by disorders with the inner ear and hearing nerve is sensorineural hearing loss. Many of these people might benefit from a cochlear

implant. These devices are surgically implanted and stimulate the hearing nerve directly, enhancing the capacity to hear and interpret speech. (*Types of hearing impairment*, 2018)

The following factors may contribute to sensorineural hearing loss:

- Illnesses.
- Drugs are harmful to one's hearing.
- A family history of hearing loss.
- Aging.
- A direct hit to the skull.

- A difficulty with the inner ear's development.
- Surround yourself with loud sounds or explosions. (American Speech-Language-Hearing Association, 2009)

Approximately 466 million people in universal are suffering by hearing loss, according to the World Health Organization (Ma et al., 2019). In the United States, roughly 66,000 new instances of sudden sensorineural hearing loss are diagnosed each year (Chandrasekhar et al., 2019). Hearing loss is caused by the degeneration of sensual hair cells, main auditory neurons, and synaptic linkages to cells themselves in the cochlea are known as sensorineural. (Ma et al., 2019)

The particular requirements of neurotrophin and other hearing loss treatments, such as high dosage, long-term management, localized or cell-specific directing, and procedures for their safe and practical conveyance to the cochlea, are being fulfilled by drug treatment delivery systems (Suzuki et al., 2016)(Du et al., 2018). Drug-based treatments based on neurotrophic factors are among the most promising for healing the ribbon synapse after noise exposure and avoiding early auditory neuron loss and regeneration of auditory neuron fibres following acute hearing loss. Using novel biomaterials, large doses of medicine may be given to the cochlea, with slow-release features that are valuable in treating hearing loss. With promising findings, new gene therapy approaches are addressing the need for cell selectivity and high effectiveness in treating both hereditary and acquired deafness (Gao et al., 2017).

Metabolic syndrome manifests as high blood pressure, abdominal obesity, high cholesterol, and diabetes. Stroke, myocardial infarction, cardiovascular mortality, and diabetes have all been related to the metabolic syndrome. Aghazadeh Attari and colleagues (Aghazadeh-Attari et al, 2017)

Literature Review

Liberman & Kujawa's research showed that exposure to loud noise, ototoxic medications, and aging are all typical reasons of hearing damage in humans, and sensory hair cells are often damaged, resulting in raised thresholds on the clinical audiogram. (Liberman & Kujawa, 2017) These therapies aim to decrease inner ear inflammation while simultaneously improving blood flow and oxygenation. For these purposes, steroids, vasodilators, plasma expanders, antiviral, and diuretic medications are used in various combinations. Hyperbaric oxygen (HBO) and low-molecular-weight heparin (LMWH) have also been demonstrated to have therapeutic benefits. (Edizer et al., 2015)

Large dose; long-term administration, targeted or cell-specific targeting, and safe and practical transport to the cochlea are some of the particular needs of neurotrophin and other hearing loss therapies. Treatments for inherited and acquired hearing loss using new gene therapy technologies have shown promising outcomes in terms of cell selectivity and efficacy. The cochlear implant is used in conjunction with a variety of biomaterials and cell therapies to guarantee that the main neurons get therapeutic benefit during electrical stimulation. (Ma et al., 2019)

Rim et al., in 2021, studied the link in hearing loss and metabolic syndrome. Hearing loss was linked to a higher number of metabolic syndrome diagnostic variables, particularly in those who had four of them: high blood pressure, obesity, high triglyceride levels, and a high fasting blood glucose level. This research emphasizes the necessity of metabolic syndrome regulation in treating hearing loss. (Rim et al., 2021) Chien et al. showed in 2015 diabetes mellitus, hypertension, and hyperlipidemia have all been linked to sudden sensorineural hearing loss. These findings imply that metabolic syndrome is a separate threat for abrupt sensorineural hearing issues in Taiwan. (Chien et al., 2015)

Relevance

The literature elaborated above is research articles and research reviews related to the different hearing loss treatments. It also describes the relation of this hearing loss with metabolic syndrome. The clinical efficiency of these treatments is also explained.

Purpose

The research goal is to estimate the efficiency of several treatments of sensorineural hearing loss. The link between sensorineural hearing loss and metabolic syndrome is explained.

Method

Clinical Trials Registry of the National Institutes of Health (NIH), PubMed, and MEDLINE collect data. Candidates hearing loss therapy were discovered via a search of the NIH Clinical Trials registry, and supportive papers were obtained from MEDLINE/PubMed. The clinical results, treatment mechanisms, and proof-of-concept were all evaluated. There were 22

ongoing clinical drug studies in United States, and six theoretically medicinal compounds were examined. Four of the six compounds examined included mechanisms for reducing oxidative stress pathways, which contribute to inner damage. One of the left over therapies attempted to regulate the cell death. The last treatment was a unique cell replacement therapy strategy that included the introduction of a transcription factor that stimulates hair cell regeneration.

Interventional clinical studies in phase 1 or later that evaluated sensorineural hearing loss were included. Steroids, natural supplements such as Gingko Biloba, therapies for illnesses other than sensorineural hearing loss (e.g., Meniere's disease, cerumen impaction, autoimmune inner ear disease, congenital CMV infection), and studies that were terminated were also eliminated.

Results

There were 22 active medical studies recorded in the United States. We looked at six possibly medicinal compounds from the 22 ongoing clinical studies. For each chemical, sufficient fundamental science and clinical data were acquired to enable a fair debate on the therapy's basis and justification. Four of the six chemicals examined dealt with methods for preventing oxidative stress, which is thought to cause auditory cell death. The final treatment was a exclusive cell replacement technique to familiarize a transcription factor that causes hair cell regeneration.

Targeting cell death ways and oxidant stresses impact on cochlear sensual neuroepithelium seems to be recurrent subject in latest clinical studies filed in US.

Furthermore, if a virus-delivered cell replacement treatment is shown to be safe and effective, it will be the first of its type. There are still significant obstacles to overcome in getting these medicines to marketplace. Furthermore, when new mechanisms associated with hearing defeat, like an immunological reaction and the failure of synaptic links, are discovered, new targets become accessible.

Conclusion

Global hearing loss is a concern. In humans, sensual hair cells are usually damaged and they do not normally heal. To combat this, many medical treatments are utilized. Drug therapy, cell replacement and gene therapy are the new treatments used worldwide to combat hearing loss. One of the methods is delivery cochlear cells with DNA coding

neurotrophic proteins. In the circular window of the cochlea, hydrogel biomaterials are being explored for non-invasive medicine delivery. SGN repopulation or neurotrophin provision for SGN defense after hearing loss has also been studied. Advances in drug treatment strategies help to transfer pre-clinical results into clinical trials. The relationship between hearing loss and metabolic syndrome is also discussed. Metabolic syndrome is directly associated with possibility of hearing defect.

Acknowledgment

I pay my heartiest gratitude to my supervisor for assisting me in compelling this research article. I am thankful to my parents, colleagues, and friends for supporting me throughout my research.

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